

Impossible Fibers Rheometer Lab Equipment Guide

Brookfield Ametek DVNext Viscometer
Model: DVN XR VDBG

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1. Turn on the viscometer using the power switch in the back (*Figure 1*).

Figure 1. The power switch of the viscometer

2. Upon powering up the viscometer, the user will be prompted to level the device, if not already level. To level the viscometer, adjust the 3 leveling screws on the base. When the device is not level, the centering dot will be red (*Figure 2, left*). While adjusting to a level position, the dot will become yellow, signifying that the device is approaching a position where it will be level. Once the dot is within specified limits of the center circle, the dot will turn green to signify that the DVNext is now level and ready to operate (*Figure 2, right*).

Figure 2. The device is not level (left) the device is level and ready to operate (right)

- When the system comes online, it will show a blue screen for ~5 seconds before automatically reaching the AutoZero start page. Remove any attached spindle to complete the AutoZero. Keep spindle end and other magnetic materials 1-inch away from the coupling during autozero. Do not touch the rheometer during the AutoZero process to ensure the best zero value. The rheometer will operate for approximately 13 seconds. After the AutoZero is complete press the Next button (Figure 3).

Figure 3. The viscometer screen after the AutoZero process is completed.

The viscometer will transition to the Configure Viscosity Test screen after you press the Next button. (If the AutoZero was performed from the Settings Menu, then the rheometer will return to the Settings Menu). You can select the home button, to go to the Main Menu, which is on the top left corner of the screen.

- Home screen shows the Main Menu functions and provides access to the following list (Figure 4)

Figure 4. Viscometer home screen (Main Menu)

Configure viscosity test : Create and run viscosity tests.

Configure yield test : Create and run yield tests.

Load test : Load a test that has previously been saved. Tests may be loaded from internal memory or a USB Flash Drive.

View results : Load Results (saved test data) that have previously been saved. Results may be loaded from internal memory or a USB Flash Drive.

Manage files : Manage the file system in the internal memory or on a USB Flash Drive for test programs and saved data.

Viscosity wizard : The Viscosity Wizard will provide a step-by-step guide to setup and run a test.

5. In the “Configure Viscosity Test” menu you can run a viscosity measurement if you know the approximate viscosity of your solution and the conditions (spindle speed) needed (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Configure Viscosity Test Screen

The process of selecting a spindle and speed for an unknown fluid is normally trial and error. An appropriate selection will result in measurements made between 10-100 on the instrument % torque scale. To measure high viscosity samples, choose a small spindle and/or a slow speed. If the chosen spindle/speed results in a reading above 100%, then reduce the speed or choose a smaller spindle.

6. If you don't know what viscosity range or appropriate measurement conditions, press the home button in the top left corner and select “Viscosity Wizard” (Figure 6).

Figure 6. The Viscosity Wizard Test Screen

This option will help you to create a run that works for your system. It allows you to select comparative liquids to the test liquid so you can get a measurement of your sample and build the testing inputs that are needed.

7. Remove the bottom cup by moving the metal stopping rod holding it in place, determine which spindle you want to use for measuring the viscosity of your samples. The 40Z spindle is meant for viscosities from 0.1cP (mPa.s) to 3000 cP (mPa.s) and the 52Z spindle is able to characterize high viscosity solutions from 3.0 cP (mPa.s) to 92,000 cP (mPa.s) (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Spindles CPM-52Z and CPM-40Z

8. The spindles attach to the rheometer magnetically, so you only need to adjust them so the base lines up and it will hold into place (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Magnetic spindle before (right) and after (left) attachment

9. Reattach the cup, and move the metal rod back under to support the sample cup (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Cup attached to the viscometer

10. Select “Set Cone Plate Gap”. From this menu, follow the instructions as prompted:
 - If the contact light (yellow) is illuminated, turn the micrometer adjustment ring clockwise (left) (as you look down on the instrument) until the light is no longer illuminated (clockwise lowers the cup, while counterclockwise raises it)
 - If the yellow contact light is not illuminated, slowly turn the micrometer adjustment ring in small increments (one or two scale divisions) counterclockwise.
 - Continue moving the micrometer adjustment ring slowly counterclockwise until the contact light (yellow) first turns on. THIS IS THE “HIT POINT.”
 - Adjust the sliding reference marker, right or left, to the closest full scale division mark.
 - Turn the micrometer adjustment ring one scale division to the left to meet the line on the sliding reference marker. THE YELLOW CONTACT LIGHT SHOULD GO

OFF. Each line on the ring represents one scale division and is equivalent to 0.0005 inch movement of the plate relative to the cone.

- You have established the gap space (0.0005 in) needed for measurement. Press ok.
- Re-establish the hit point every time the spindle is attached/detached.

11. Whether using the “Viscosity Wizard” or “Configure Viscosity Test” option, when you have determined the conditions for your test and set cone plate gap, to load a sample you need to remove the bottom cup again..

12. Remove the cup carefully and dispense 0.5mL of the solution you want to measure the viscosity of directly into the center of the cup, which will be below the spindle (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Sample in the center of the cup

13. Attach the sample cup carefully and attach the probe and allow for the system to equilibrate if there is a temperature difference.

14. Double check the parameters, enter the sample name, and then click “Run”

15. When the measurement is done, press Ok and save the viscosity data from the run both in the internal memory and flash drive. (If ‘Single point’ data collection is selected, viscometer collects only a single data point when the End Condition is met.)

16. When the test is finished, remove the cup and clean it using soap and water and then wipe with a kimwipe with 70% IPA and dry it. Do the same with the spindle, and put it back in the correct case for it. Reattach the cup.

17. Turn off the power.

(For more detailed operation, the user guide provided by Brookfield Engineering can be found [here](#).)